

Quantum Time Removal Within a Wavelength and Reflection/Refraction

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The problem of an incident beam of light traveling to the right in the x direction and reflecting/ refracting at an interface at $x=0$ may be solved using Maxwell's electromagnetic equation for the electric field of a photon. In particular, mathematical continuity of the electric field and its first derivative, where the field is of the form $\text{Real}(\exp(ipx - iEt))$ with E energy being constant, but p allowed to change, may be used to establish relationships between weights of the incident, reflected and refracted electric fields. The modulus of each of these waves is then linked to intensity.

The above continuity equation, however, is somewhat unusual if one thinks of a single quantum traveling in time. For instance, before it strikes it is an incident photon, but after (in time) it is either a reflected or refracted one. Thus probability naturally appears in the problem and if one performs the usual grouping by time, then the incident photon is on one side and the reflected or refracted on the other. This is the opposite grouping used in the continuity approach so we ask: How may this be understood?

On average a photon moves with a certain speed, but it also has a wavelength. We argued in (2) that for a particle with rest mass, there is no time within the wavelength region, but rather a probability to be at an x value is given by $\exp(ipx)$. In fact, the two dimensional nature of $\exp(ipx)$ accounts for the removal of time as one needs two "variables" or dimensions to describe the direction of motion. On average, however, the particle still moves as $x=\text{velocity time}$. If there is no time in the probabilistic approach within a wavelength, then even treating the particle as a point means that there is no clear separation in time of the incident, reflected and refracted rays. If one uses space as a marker (as in the time-independent Schrodinger approach to a bound quantum particle) then this spatial approach within a wavelength governs the solution to the problem.

In such a case, one may write $A\exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) = C\exp(ip_2 x)$ and a similar conservation of momentum equation $A p \exp(ipx) - p B \exp(-ipx) = C p_2 \exp(ip_2 x)$ rather than argue that the electric field and its derivative should be continuous at $x=0$. We use addition because there exists an OR situation, but we do not employ the usual grouping by time, but rather in space with this probability. On average, however, this approach must be consistent with $AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2$ where A^*A etc are intensity values much like $W^*(x)W(x)=\text{Probability}(x)$ for a bound particle where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction.

Mathematically the above approach is the same as the continuity of the electric field and its first derivative, but we suggest that this view considers the role of time in the problem. The continuity approach allows for the incident, reflected and refracted photon to exist at the same time which only makes sense if time does not really exist within a wavelength, even though there is a mapping to $x=vt$. Thus both the loss of time and the idea of probability are needed and they complement each other.

Electric Field Continuity and the Reflection/Refraction of Light

If one were to follow a quantum of light i.e. a photon in time (moving to the right along the x axis), which is the Newtonian or special relativistic scenario), it would be an incident photon for a time range until it struck a surface at $x=0$. After that, it would be either a reflected or refracted photon. Thus there is a probability governing whether the photon reflects or refracts.

Maxwell's electromagnetic equations lead to two wave equations, one for the electric field and one for the magnetic, for a photon solution (i.e. no sources, currents). This object travels with the speed of light in a vacuum, based on parameters appearing in Maxwell's equations. The form of the electric field (an example) is:

Electric field = $A \cos(px-wt)$ ((1)) (The particle travels in the x direction and the electric and magnetic fields are oscillatory and perpendicular to each other and the direction of motion.

For mathematical simplicity it is often represented by: $A \exp(ipx-iwt)$.

A traditional approach is to impose continuity of the electric field and its first derivative at an interface. After all, Maxwell's equations deal with electric and magnetic fields which exist in space and their various derivatives. Such a mathematical approach is fine for electric fields if one does not think of a photon as a point entity traveling in x and t i.e. $x(x) \rightarrow x=ct$. In such a case one would not necessarily consider adding quantities which exist at different times which is exactly what is done when considering continuity in space while ignoring time. The incident and reflected beams exist for $x<0$, the interface is at $x=0$ and the refracted beam at $x>0$. Continuity means associating the incident and reflected beams together and equating them to the refracted beam. This seems like a contradiction to the notion of following the photon in time.

Nevertheless we present the brief calculation as given in (1):

$$A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ip_2 x) \quad (\text{incident+reflected} = \text{refracted}) \quad ((2a))$$

$$\text{Continuity of the derivative yields: } Ap \exp(ipx) - p \exp(-ipx) B = C p_2 \exp(ip_2 x) \quad ((2b))$$

$$\text{Setting } x=0 \text{ yields: } A+B=C \quad ((3a)) \text{ and } A-B= C p_2/p \quad ((3b))$$

For a photon $E=pc$ so for E constant: $p_2/p = c_2/c_1$. As shown in (1) this yields:

$$B/A = (c_2-c_1)/(c_2+c_1) \quad ((4a)) \text{ and } C/A = 2c_2/(c_1+c_2) \quad ((4b))$$

For $c_2-c_1<0$, there exists a phase shift of 180 degrees for the reflected ray. Linking with a particle conservation of energy picture one has:

$$AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2 \quad ((5))$$

In ((5)) one reverts back to the “time” picture i.e. the incident beam A represents the energy for the time interval before hitting the interface and B and C represent the two different types of energies after the collision.

Thus two types of time scenarios are really being used in the above approach. By stating that one uses continuity of the electric field and its derivative one does not mention time, but it does not disappear only to reappear in ((5)). Thus we argue that one needs a picture which explains what is happening to time in ((2a)) and ((2b)) versus ((5)).

Furthermore probability exists in this picture and the continuity approach, although including the electric field of both reflected and refracted beams does not mention probability.

Loss of Time Within a Wavelength and Probability

Both light and quantum particles with rest mass have a wavelength. In the case of light, the existence of a wavelength was known in the early 1800s, while it took until the 1920s for a particle with rest mass’s wavelength to be seen. The question we ask is: What are the dynamics within a wavelength for a particle moving with constant speed? If the particle moves with constant speed one would assume that within a wavelength one should at least have average motion of $x=vt$. This begs the question: Why have a wavelength at all if Newtonian dynamics exists for all x ? The experimental fact is that it does not because there are diffraction/interference results. Thus within a wavelength the particle is still a point and if it strikes another particle it does so with a constant momentum of p , but there is no time and the particle is described by a probability to be at x i.e. $\exp(ipx)$. This probability is complex because it must be associated with two dimensions, one representing x and the other the effect of t (i.e. a probability shift) so that the direction of motion may be distinguished.

The fact that the wavelength is real and represents an absence of time, we argue, has important physical consequences on a boundary type problem such as an incident photon hitting a surface at $x=0$. On average, a time picture must still hold as it does in ((5)), but given that the incident, reflected and refracted beams have wavelengths with an absence of time, then when dealing with wavelengths one cannot break the problem into two time pieces, i.e. a “before striking the interface” and “after striking”. One only has probabilities in x with no time present. This means the incident and reflected beams must be associated because they exist in the same x region ($x<0$) while the refracted exists in $x>0$. Furthermore this is a probability problem as $\exp(ipx)$ is a probability, but also because a single incident becomes either a reflected or a refracted one. With probabilities an OR situation implies addition except that one does not add according to the usual time separation because time does not exist (except on average). Thus treating $\exp(ipx)$ as a probability and using weights A,B,C for the incident, reflected and refracted beams, one has:

$$A\exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) \quad x<0 \quad \text{and} \quad C\exp(ip_2 x) \quad x>0 \quad ((6))$$

At $x=0$, the two pieces of ((6)) representing probability come together to conserve this unusual probability i.e.

$$A + B = C \quad ((7a)) \quad \text{at } x=0$$

Furthermore one may use conservation of momentum also at $x=0$ i.e.

$$A-B = Cp^2/p \quad ((7b))$$

These are the same equations as given in the case of mathematical continuity of the electric field, but now we consider probability and time directly i.e. we assume an absence of time and a probability existing in x together with the idea of an OR probability. We argue that the fact that one included both reflected and refracted electric fields in the mathematical electromagnetic argument already implies probability because a single photon (which has electric and magnetic fields) does not simultaneously become both a reflected and refracted photon and experiments exist which allow one to manipulate light one photon at a time.

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that using mathematical continuity of the electric field and its first derivative in a reflection/refraction problem and then associating this with before and after interface collision energies (i.e. a time picture) raises questions as to the behaviour of time and probability in the continuity approach. We note that probability is also contained with the continuity picture because a single photon either becomes a reflected OR a refracted one. Both electric fields appear with no mention of probability except perhaps through the weights, but not using an expression for probability.

We note that continuity deals only with association in x space, but not in time, thus the incident and reflected light is grouped together and equated with the refracted one at $x=0$. This is the opposite grouping which occurs using progression in time, which presumably occurs in a simple photon as a classical particle picture. One may then ask why time is ignored in the mathematical continuity approach? We also note that continuity of the first derivative d/dx is linked to a kind of momentum conservation. Thus we try to describe this problem in a different manner, one which explicitly includes probabilities, deals with time and explains why only the first derivative need be continuous.

We argue that light, like particles with rest mass, have a wavelength. Within this wavelength there is no time (except on average), the particle is a point with momentum p , but can be at different x points with the probability $\exp(ipx)$. Two dimensions are needed to account for the missing time and yet still describe the direction of motion. Given that one deals with probabilities, OR situations add, but one cannot use time as a separator because it does not exist within a wavelength (only on average). Thus one associates the incident and reflected wave probabilities together for $x<0$ and leaves the refracted for $x>0$. At $x=0$ probability is conserved so: $A\exp(ipx)+B\exp(-ipx) = C \exp(i p^2 x)$ and conservation of momentum in this scheme which does not use time is: $A p \exp(ipx) - pB\exp(ipx) = Cp^2 \exp(ip2x)$. This is why only the first derivative applies.

Thus one does not need a continuity argument to solve this problem, but may think in terms of x probabilities, the absence of time and OR situations leading to addition. Probability and average momentum are conserved, but not using the usual grouping in time, because time has been removed in x probability scheme.

References

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